

Release of P_2O_5 and CaO from some Indian Basic Slags in Aqueous Medium in the Presence of Decomposable Organic Substances

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It has been observed that the availability of phosphate and lime to plants from the basic slags available from different steel plants of India e.g., Burnpur, Bhadrabati Open-hearth Furnace, Bhadrabati Electric Furnace, Rourkela, Durgapur, Tata and Bhilai basic slags can be increased in the presence of decomposing organic matter. The results also show that the amount of lime and P_2O_5 passing into the solution with all these basic slags gradually increases with the lapse of time and is always more in the presence of decomposing organic matter than with water alone. The effectiveness of various organic substances in increasing the P_2O_5 and lime solubility of the slags can be arranged in the order of D-glucose > mangoleaves > sawdust > paddy straw.

THE application of organic matter to improve the fertility of soil with phosphates has been studied by a large number of workers¹⁻¹⁰ all over the world. Havanagi and Mann¹¹ remarked that the availability of phosphate in soil markedly increases by the application of farmyard manure. Recently some workers¹²⁻¹⁴ have studied the effect of decomposing organic matter on the solubility of some sparingly soluble phosphates, basic slag and rock phosphates. Ramulu and Prath¹⁵ reported that the solubility of dicalcium phosphate increases in the presence of organic matter. Mandal and Jha¹⁶ after 10 years of extensive laboratory and field studies have remarked that Indian basic slags can be used as a liming material in acidic soils whether they contain P_2O_5 or not.

So far no significant work has been carried to study the efficiency of different Indian basic slags in the presence of decomposing organic matter from the P_2O_5 and lime solubilization view point. Therefore, in the present paper an attempt has been made to determine the solubility of different Indian basic slags i.e., Burnpur, Bhadrabati Open-hearth Furnace, Bhadrabati Electric Furnace, Rourkela, Durgapur,

Tata and Bhilai basic slags in the presence of decomposing organic matter like D-glucose, mango-leaves, saw dust and paddy straw.

Experimental

Basic slags used in these experiments were powdered, sieved through a 100-mesh sieve and analysed for different constituents¹⁷. 1 gm each of basic slag was taken in different Jena-glass bottles and to them were added 100 ml of double distilled water or along with 0.5 g of carbon as D-glucose, mango leaves, saw dust or paddy straw. The bottles were kept in a thermostat maintained at $30^\circ \pm 1^\circ$. The moisture content was also maintained constant throughout the experiment. The bottles were stirred daily. Different sets were used for different intervals of time (1, 20, 40, 60, 80, 100, 150, 200, 250 and 300 days). After fixed interval of time the bottles were shaken for 1 hr in a mechanical shaker and then allowed to stand for some time. The contents were filtered and the filtrates were utilized for determining pH, P_2O_5 ¹⁸ and lime¹⁸. For the estimation of P_2O_5 , 25 ml of the filtrates were evaporated to dryness in a conical flask with 5 ml of concentrated nitric acid. The process was repeated till whole of the organic matter was oxidised. The

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TABLE I—ANALYSIS OF DIFFERENT INDIAN BASIC SLAGS

%	Bur.B.S.	Bha.O.B.S.	Bha.E.B.S.	R.B.S.	D.B.S.	T.B.S.	Bhi.B.S.
SiO ₂	15.957	25.022	29.529	33.118	27.159	14.605	20.513
FeO	19.309	10.213	1.638	0.585	5.544	28.001	9.324
MnO	4.681	10.472	1.238	2.524	5.001	3.204	9.145
CaO	41.719	39.390	34.100	33.330	36.053	32.732	43.492
P ₂ O ₅	3.584	0.884	0.517	0.260	3.214	7.841	1.497
Al ₂ O ₃	7.389	1.617	23.898	23.120	16.016	6.445	5.628
MgO	6.382	11.459	8.890	6.235	6.282	6.236	9.453
Available P ₂ O ₅ (2% Citric acid)	1.923	0.432	0.251	0.142	1.670	4.025	0.786

residue was dissolved in hot dil, nitric acid, diluted by adding 25 ml of distilled water and the P₂O₅ content was estimated volumetrically by precipitating the phosphorus as ammonium phosphomolybdate at 40° by adding excess of ammonium molybdate solution. In case where the amount of P₂O₅ to be estimated was small, colorimetric¹⁹ method was used.

The lime content of the filtrate was determined volumetrically by ammonium oxalate method after oxidising the organic matter present in 25 ml of the filtrate with repeated evaporation to dryness with 5 ml of concentrated nitric acid and dissolving the residue in hot dil. HCl.

The pH of the filtrates was determined by a portable Cambridge pH-meter.

To make the paper short only the results obtained after 24 hr and 300 days have been mentioned.

The following abbreviations have been used for different Indian basic slags and also for organic matter.

Burnpur basic slag (Bur. B.S.), Bhadrabati Open-hearth Furnace basic slag (Bha. O.B.S.), Bhadrabati Electric Furnace basic slag (Bha. E.B.S.), Rourkela basic slag (R.B.S.), Durgapur basic slag (D.B.S.), Tata basic slag (T.B.S.), Bhilai basic slag (Bhi. B.S.), D-glucose (D.G.), Mango leaves (M.L.), Saw dust (S.D.) and Paddy straw (P.S.).

TABLE 2—ANALYSIS OF DIFFERENT ORGANIC MATTERS

%	D-Glucose	Mango Leaves	Saw dust	Paddy straw
Carbon	40.000	50.480	49.230	43.340
CaO	×	1.214	1.171	0.742
MgO	×	1.332	1.231	0.224
P ₂ O ₅	×	0.242	0.243	0.402

TABLE 3—SOLUBILITY OF BASIC SLAGS IN WATER

Sample	After 24 hr.		
	pH	S. of P ₂ O ₅ g/l	S. of lime g/l
Bur. B.S.	9.05	0.00278	0.08764
Bha. O.B.S.	9.15	0.00085	0.06946
Bha. E.B.S.	7.95	0.00045	0.02277
R.B.S.	7.65	0.00021	0.02092
D.B.S.	10.40	0.00266	0.09094
T.B.S.	8.30	0.00688	0.04583
Bhi. B.S.	10.75	0.00136	0.10473

TABLE 4
After 300 days

Sample	pH	S. of P ₂ O ₅ g/l	S. of lime g/l
Bur. B.S.	10.60	0.00546	0.14823
Bha. O.B.S.	10.70	0.00181	0.14201
Bha. E.B.S.	9.10	0.00083	0.05401
R.B.S.	9.05	0.00045	0.05123
D.B.S.	11.20	0.00537	0.18487
T.B.S.	9.70	0.01165	0.10055
Bhi. B.S.	11.35	0.00262	0.18634

TABLE 5—D-GLUCOSE SYSTEM

After 24 hr.

Sample	pH	S. of P ₂ O ₅ g/l	S. of lime g/l
Bur. B.S.	8.75	0.00457	0.11542
Bha. O.B.S.	8.85	0.00133	0.10543
Bha. E.B.S.	7.60	0.00085	0.03532
R.B.S.	7.40	0.00045	0.03213
D.B.S.	10.00	0.00426	0.12034
T.B.S.	7.90	0.00812	0.06535
Bhi. B.S.	10.30	0.00233	0.15036

TABLE 6

After 300 days

Sample	pH	S. of P ₂ O ₅ g/l	S. of lime g/l
Bur. B.S.	6.40	0.03366	0.76542
Bha. O.B.S.	6.50	0.00963	0.65145
Bha. E.B.S.	5.80	0.00371	0.32128
R.B.S.	5.70	0.00455	0.30236
D.B.S.	6.80	0.03184	0.82064
T.B.S.	5.85	0.11047	0.63155
Bhi. B.S.	7.05	0.01626	0.99870

TABLE 7—MANGO LEAVES SYSTEM

After 24 hr.

Sample	pH	S. of P ₂ O ₅ g/l	S. of lime g/l
Bur. B.S.	8.80	0.00399	0.11042
Bha. O.B.S.	8.90	0.00122	0.09986
Bha. E.B.S.	7.70	0.00081	0.03227
R.B.S.	7.50	0.00042	0.02946
D.B.S.	10.15	0.00375	0.11524
T.B.S.	8.00	0.00782	0.06145
Bhi. B.S.	10.50	0.00199	0.14023

TABLE 8

After 300 days

Sample	pH	S. of P ₂ O ₅ g/l	S. of lime g/l
Bur. B.S.	6.60	0.02871	0.71542
Bha. O.B.S.	6.70	0.00845	0.61633
Bha. E.B.S.	6.20	0.00765	0.29526
R.B.S.	6.10	0.00412	0.28557
D.B.S.	7.20	0.02802	0.76048
T.B.S.	6.35	0.09943	0.60047
Bhi. B.S.	7.30	0.01454	0.86490

TABLE 9—SAW DUST SYSTEM

After 24 hr.

Sample	pH	S. of P ₂ O ₅ g/l	S. of lime g/l
Bur. B.S.	8.90	0.00341	0.10537
Bha. O.B.S.	8.95	0.00105	0.09028
Bha. E.B.S.	7.80	0.00075	0.03034
R.B.S.	7.55	0.00036	0.02815
D.B.S.	10.25	0.00324	0.11236
T.B.S.	8.15	0.00755	0.05548
Bhi. B.S.	10.65	0.00171	0.13024

TABLE 10
After 300 days

Sample	pH	S. of P ₂ O ₅ g/l	S. of lime g/l
Bur. B.S.	6.85	0.02441	0.69022
Bha. O.B.S.	7.05	0.00708	0.56133
Bha. E.B.S.	6.40	0.00633	0.28482
R.B.S.	6.25	0.00326	0.26548
D.B.S.	7.50	0.02224	0.71537
T.B.S.	6.55	0.08512	0.53603
Bhi. B.S.	7.60	0.01324	0.75988

TABLE 11—PADDY STRAW SYSTEM

After 24 hr.

Sample	pH	S. of P ₂ O ₅ g/l	S. of lime g/l
Bur. B.S.	9.00	0.00302	0.09543
Bha. O.B.S.	9.10	0.00095	0.08498
Bha. E.B.S.	7.90	0.00061	0.02846
R.B.S.	7.60	0.00032	0.02543
D.B.S.	10.35	0.00285	0.10542
T.B.S.	8.25	0.00714	0.05147
Bhi. B.S.	10.75	0.00152	0.12498

TABLE 12

After 300 days

Sample	pH	S. of P ₂ O ₅ g/l	S. of lime g/l
Bur. B.S.	7.35	0.02265	0.60124
Bha. O.B.S.	7.50	0.00631	0.48496
Bha. E.B.S.	6.85	0.00511	0.25513
R.B.S.	6.60	0.00302	0.23345
D.B.S.	8.35	0.02026	0.63014
T.B.S.	7.05	0.07712	0.42543
Bhi. B.S.	8.65	0.01223	0.66047

Discussion

The experimental results recorded in tables (6 to 11) show that the solubility of different Indian basic slags markedly increases in the presence of decomposing organic substances like D-glucose, mango leaves, saw dust and paddy straw which undergo slow oxidation in air at ordinary temperature and their hydrolysis continues for several days. It has been invariably observed that the solubility of all the slags is always more in the presence of decomposing organic matter than in water alone for the same period. The results show that with T.B.S. the amount of lime and P₂O₅ passing into the solution is 0.04583 and 0.00688 g/l in water and 0.06535 and 0.00812 g/l with D-glucose system after 24-hr and after 300 days the values are 0.10055 and 0.01165 g/l in water and 0.63155 and 0.11047 g/l with D-glucose system respectively. Thus there is an increase in the amounts of lime and P₂O₅ passing into the solution from T.B.S. due to D-glucose which is 0.01952 and 0.00124 g/l only after 24 hr and after 300-days the values are 0.53100 and 0.09882 g/l respectively. Like T.B.S. the solubility of phosphate and lime of

other Indian basic slags is always more in the presence of D-glucose than in water alone. Similar type of results have been obtained with mango leaves, saw dust and paddy straw. The effectiveness of various sources of organic matter in increasing the P₂O₅ and lime solubility of basic slags can be arranged in the decreasing order of D-glucose > mango leaves > saw dust > paddy straw. The varying effect of these organic substances on the solubility of basic slags is due to the fact that D-glucose being a soluble carbohydrate gets easily oxidised. Mango leaves may contain some soluble organic compounds as well as cellulosic material which may be less easily oxidised than D-glucose but more readily than saw dust and paddy straw which may contain high lignin content. The percentage of lignin content may be more in paddy straw than in saw dust, therefore, saw dust may get easily oxidised than paddy straw. The increase in the P₂O₅ and lime solubility of basic slag in the presence of these organic substances is due to the fact that organic matter undergoes slow oxidation in air to form various acids^{13,20} e.g., acetic acid, tartaric acid, oxalic acid, citric acid, pyruvic acid and butyric acid as intermediate products and carbonic acid as final product which are mainly responsible in increasing the solubility of slags. The dissolving action of various acids formed during the oxidation and decomposition of organic matter upon the P₂O₅ solubility of basic slags can be explained on the basis of their dissociation constants¹⁸ and the structural characteristics^{21, 22, 23} of the anions of various organic acids involved.

It has been observed that the pH of the solutions decreases with lapse of time. With D-glucose system the pH of the solution obtained in the case of T.B.S. falls from 8.30 in water to 7.90 after one day and this value continues to decrease to 5.85 after 300 days. Similar decrease in pH has been observed in all other cases. A close examination of the pH values recorded in the present paper reveals that the maximum decrease in the pH values occur with D-glucose system followed by mango leaves, saw dust and paddy straw systems. Similar trend occurs in the release of P₂O₅ in the solution by these systems. This indicates that there is a definite correlation between the pH of the system and the amount of P₂O₅ in the dissolved state. More the solution is acidic more is the amount of P₂O₅ in the dissolved state. The fall in the pH values with all the systems is due to the formation of various acids during the decomposition and oxidation of these organic substances. The fall in the pH values may also be due to the release of more P₂O₅ than lime into the solution with all the four systems.

From the experimental observations recorded in the present paper it may be seen that when basic slags mixed with decomposing organic matter will be added to soil as a fertilizer, they can supply more lime and P₂O₅ to plants than they are added alone. Besides supplying P₂O₅ and lime to plants, slags are also rich in iron, potassium, manganese, magnesium

etc., which are also needed for the efficient growth of plants and therefore they can be used for the purpose of correcting soil deficiencies of these elements

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